

Journal of Scholarly Graduate Research

The Official Journal of the Institute of the Graduate Studies

Volume 1, Issue 1

January to December, 2023 Edition

Understanding the Factors Influencing Prenatal Care Utilization and Maternal Health Services Satisfaction: Insights from Pregnant Women's Attitude and Experiences

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the relationship between numerous characteristics, attitudes, pregnancy experiences, and pregnant women's satisfaction with prenatal care utilization. Prenatal care is critical to mothers' and babies' health and well-being. Understanding the factors influencing pregnant women's satisfaction with prenatal care is essential for enhancing care quality. The research used a correlational approach. A representative group of pregnant women from various backgrounds was recruited, and data on their utilization of prenatal care, attitudes toward care providers, pregnancy experiences, and overall satisfaction were collected. Statistical methods like weighted mean and partial least square- structural equation modeling was used to investigate the relationship between these factors and levels of satisfaction. It was found that several factors have a substantial impact on pregnant women's satisfaction with prenatal care. Quality and accessibility of care, relationship with healthcare practitioners, psychological support, continuity of care, and readiness as part of physical well-being are among these variables. Furthermore, attitudes toward caregivers, such as perceived empathy and respect, are essential in determining satisfaction levels. This study complements the existing literature by thoroughly understanding the interaction between factors, attitudes, pregnancy experiences, and satisfaction with prenatal care utilization. The research results have implications for healthcare policy and practice, emphasizing the value of improving prenatal care quality while increasing patient satisfaction.

Keywords: Pregnancy experiences, Utilization of prenatal care, Psychosocial, Psychological, Attitudes

How to Cite (APA): Baluyot, M.M. & Gadia, E.D. (2023). Understanding the factors influencing prenatal care utilization and maternal health services satisfaction: Insights from pregnant women's attitude and experiences. *Journal of Scholarly Graduate Research*, 1(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14759259>

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a significant time to encourage a healthy lifestyle and psychologically and emotionally prepare women and their families for parental responsibility. Pregnancy, also known as gestation, is the stage of development when one or more children grow inside a woman.

According to the World Health Organization (2016), prenatal care is defined as the care provided by skilled healthcare providers to pregnant women and adolescent girls to ensure the best health conditions for both mother and baby during pregnancy.

Similarly, Backe et al., (2016) identified prenatal care as the routine health supervision of apparently healthy pregnant women without symptoms (screening), intending to diagnose diseases or impede obstetric circumstances without symptoms, as well as providing information about lifestyle, pregnancy, and delivery. Moreso, Konje, et al. (2018) stated that one of the "four pillars" of safe motherhood initiatives is prenatal care, which encourages and helps to establish good health throughout pregnancy and the initial postpartum

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period. Good prenatal care promotes the preservation and general wellbeing of mothers and babies. Prenatal care also allows women to communicate with their healthcare provider and increases the likelihood that they will employ a skilled birth attendant.

Prenatal care is required for all pregnant women. A doctor, midwife, or other health care professional can provide prenatal care. Prenatal care is necessary to monitor a pregnancy's progress and identify potential problems before they become serious for either mom or baby. Pregnant women who receive adequate prenatal care have healthy and balanced babies and are less inclined to give birth prematurely. With appropriate prenatal care, the chances of developing severe pregnancy problems are also reduced.

While the utilization of maternal and child health services in the Philippines has been satisfactory as indicated by Asio (2019), the emphasis on the poor has remained low, as evidenced by considerable disparities in usage patterns across economic classes and regions. It is doable that as the nationwide average for healthcare utilization improves, only those in the highest income group will benefit, while the poor will remain marginalized. Acknowledging the patterns of inequality within a region can assist in creating relevant policies to increase the availability and accessibility of health care.

A new report on maternal mortality reveals the dangers women in developing countries confront during pregnancy and childbirth. Year after year, approximately 4,500 women die in the Philippines as a direct consequence of pregnancy and childbirth health problems and complications (WHO, 2019). This is due to insufficient public reproductive health services, so very few mothers have received skilled care before, during, and after pregnancy, and most mothers are not constantly experiencing access to quality emergency obstetric care services. Although more than 90% of Filipino mothers seek prenatal care, only 60% of babies are delivered by adequately trained skilled birth attendants, and less than 40% are produced in public or private health care facilities.

A large percentage of pregnancy-related deaths are avoidable. Better health care, particularly during pregnancy, delivery, and postpartum, is extremely important for mitigating them. They could perhaps recognize the significance of visiting a health center for a prenatal check-up.

By and large, most Filipino families regard health as a goal, with medical and technological intervention strategies serving as a means to keep or eliminate disease agents and health conditions from their members. Measure to protect and promote an individual's health change as they progress through life. As a result, the life cycle framework is the cornerstone for designing health programs and delivering health services to specific age groups and vulnerable communities with special healthcare needs.

Since its discovery in late 2019, the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) that causes COVID-19 has spread rapidly, spurring the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare the disease a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. As a result, governments worldwide have had to react and adapt immediately to halt the virus's propagation and provide medical services to people who have been infected. The pressure placed on healthcare systems by the outbreak unquestionably impacts the reproductive and sexual health of people in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) like the Philippines. Nevertheless, reproductive, and sexual wellbeing have also been affected by societal responses to the disease outbreak, such as regional or national lockdowns that compel health care services to close down when they aren't considered necessary, as well as the repercussions of physical distancing, travel restrictions and currency depreciation.

The COVID-19 disease is a burgeoning infectious disease, together with a re-emerging viral respiratory infection that has directly impacted most countries around the world and is becoming increasingly common. The virus is rapidly spreading across the globe, prompting the World Health Organization (WHO) to classify it as a communicable pandemic disease. Despite massive efforts to contain the epidemic, nearly 5 million individuals have been reported to have outsourced the infection worldwide.

The situation of the massive global COVID-19 outbreak is disturbing. Individuals over 60 years old and those with a weakened immune system are much more vulnerable to the disease, and pregnant women are

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more susceptible to viral infections and complications; thus, a COVID-19 pandemic may have severe consequences. Unfortunately, the information available on the effects of COVID-19 on pregnancy and its possible complications has seemed inadequate. However, because of physiological changes in the maternal immune and cardiopulmonary systems, pregnant women are more likely to develop severe illness following respiratory virus infection.

Reviews of studies have shown that clinical signs, laboratory results, and radiographic criteria in pregnant women with COVID-19 are similar to other affected adults. However, the risk of developing COVID-19 disease in pregnant women is high for the reasons stated above, and there is the possibility of complications in pregnancy and newborn infection. These factors have led to anxiety and stress in pregnant women and their families.

Thereby, these predicaments prompted the researcher to undertake this investigation to assess pregnant women's attitudes, experiences and level of satisfaction towards prenatal care and other necessary medical procedures to maintain their good health, including the baby's.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the quantitative, descriptive-correlational research method was used. A descriptive correlational study is one in which the researcher primarily describes relationships between variables rather than attempting to establish a causal relationship. Stangor (2011) defined correlational research as determining relationships between variables and forecast future events based on current knowledge. Asio (2021) also described correlational research as a type of non-experimental research design.

Meanwhile, according to Creswell (2012), "a correlation is a statistical test that determines the tendency or pattern for two (or more) variables or two sets of data to vary consistently." Similarly, Ary, et al. (2010) described that correlational research intends to the relationship or correlation between positive or negative variables, with the correlation coefficient's level of correlation. The correlation coefficient was used to detect the correlation between variables.

Henceforth, correlation analysis was used. A correlational research design examines the relationship between two variables without involving the researcher in their manipulation. For example, in the paper of Rivera and Asio (2023), they employed descriptive correlation design for the link between their respondents' demographic profile and their reason for Progestin Subdermal Implant (PSI) use. Correlation is a statistical technique used to determine whether and how strongly two variables are related. It also assesses the strength or significance of the two variables' linear relationship. Indeed, it looks to see if an increase or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in another. A correlational study's findings allow researchers to determine whether or not two variables change together and to what extent. A positive correlation occurs when two variables change in the same direction. Similarly, respondents' attitudes may be positively correlated with their level of satisfaction with maternal health care services provided.

Conversely, a negative correlation occurs when two variables change in opposite directions. A negative attitude of respondents toward prenatal care instruments, for example, may be associated with a low level of satisfaction with maternal health care services provided.

The study also determined the respondents' relationship to their pregnancy experience, the factors influencing their prenatal care utilization, and their attitude toward prenatal care utilization during the pandemic. Furthermore, it sought to ascertain the relationship between respondents' attitudes toward prenatal care utilization and their level of satisfaction with the maternal health care services provided in Barangay Central Health Center.

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Respondents/ Participants

The respondents were 50 pregnant women residing in Barangay Central, Balanga City, Bataan. Random sampling was applied to identify the respondents. Total enumeration was employed in this study since all the pregnant women living in Barangay Central was chosen as the respondents.

Instrumentation

The researcher used community needs assessment and researcher-made survey questionnaires to gather information from the respondents to address the research objectives. The contents of each questionnaire were validated for appropriateness and accuracy by experts in this field. The experts consisted of a Maternal and Child Health (MCH) Coordinator, a Public Health Nurse, and a City Health Physician in Balanga City. The data were collected using the survey questionnaire. Specifically, the questionnaire was composed of four parts. Part I includes the questions in factors affecting the utilization of prenatal care among pregnant women of Barangay Central in terms of psychological factors, psychosocial factors, physical factors. Part II includes the respondent's attitude in terms of attitude towards the completion of scheduled prenatal check-up and their attitude and behavior towards COVID-19. Part III includes items regarding the pregnancy experiences of the respondents in terms of check-ups by a general practitioner and their human relations in the barangay health center and information received during pregnancy care. Part IV includes respondents' satisfaction level with the maternal health care services provided in Barangay Central Health Center.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The current study used quantitative data with two instruments—the community needs assessment and research-made survey questionnaire. The tabulated data in Microsoft Excel were treated using Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 20 (IBM- SPSS v.20) and Warp PLS version 8 software. Manual calculations were disregarded; thus, presentation of formula is not necessary.

The study utilized weighted Mean to describe the factors affecting the utilization of prenatal care, attitude of pregnant women towards the completion of scheduled prenatal check-ups, and pregnancy experiences of expectant mothers towards the level of satisfaction on the maternal health care services. This were processed using IBM-SPSS version 20.

Likewise, Partial Least Square- Structural Equation Modelling was used to test the effects of the factors affecting the utilization of prenatal care, attitude of pregnant women towards the completion of scheduled prenatal check-ups, and pregnancy experiences of expectant mothers towards the level of satisfaction on the maternal health care services. The level of significance used is 0.05 and data were processed using Warp PLS version 8 software.

Ethical Consideration

The consent forms were included on the survey questionnaires that was given to the respondents. The respondents have a right to participate or withdraw at any time without costing them anything. The researcher also kept in mind the Data Privacy Act or the Republic Act 10173 which ensures the respondent's privacy of information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main objective of this study is to understand the factors influencing prenatal care utilization and maternal health services satisfaction. This section showcases the results from the gathered data.

Factors affecting the utilization of Prenatal Care

Psychological factors. The study showed that participants are afraid to undergo prenatal care because it entails expenses, with a mean score of 2.84. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 1.98 represents that participants do not have a history of miscarriage. The overall mean indicates that, on average, individuals in this group tend to disagree with the provided statements. This suggests a general lack of agreement or alignment with the psychological factors presented. This is corroborated by the findings of Akinwaare and Oluwatosin (2019), who discovered that fear of the expense of prenatal care was a psychological component that prevented women from seeking and utilizing these services. The concern of costs was noted as a barrier that led to prenatal care delays or avoidance, potentially jeopardizing the health and well-being of pregnant women and their unborn children.

Psychosocial factors. The study determined that the ratings, on average, individuals in this group do not perceive themselves to be significantly affected by the psychosocial factors mentioned. This suggests a relatively favorable psychosocial environment in terms of preferring to stay and spend time alone due to financial burden with the highest mean score of 2.24, social support (1.60), absence of domestic violence (1.48), resource availability (1.98), and losing confidentiality (1.72), which may contribute positively to the utilization of prenatal care. However, Ziblim et al. (2018) identified critical factors influencing prenatal care utilization, including access to healthcare services, the availability and quality of prenatal care facilities, distance to healthcare facilities, and transportation constraints. Likewise, Atukunda et al. (2020) enumerated financial restrictions, fear of abuse in healthcare facilities, a lack of information or access to expert care, and perceived social support from family and community members are all factors.

Physical factors. The respondents' ratings suggest a general disagreement, with a mean score of 1.94, with the presented statements related to physical factors and pregnancy. This means that, on average, respondents do not share the concerns or experiences indicated in the statements, reflecting a positive attitude on their physical readiness, health, productivity, age-related issues, and pregnancy discomfort. Weschler's (2022) study backs up the findings by emphasizing the necessity of focusing on fertility awareness and reproductive health, providing vital information on physical fitness for pregnancy, and recognizing one's body's indications and signals. Meanwhile, Westbrook (2018) addressed physical preparation for pregnancy, age-related hazards, and usual discomforts. It provides a data-driven approach to pregnant decision-making. Thus, prenatal care is critical for the health of pregnant women and their unborn children. Positive pregnancy experiences and regular care attendance are influenced by psychological aspects such as mental health and emotional well-being. Psychosocial factors such as social support and cultural beliefs influence healthcare-seeking habits, whereas physical factors such as maternal health and discomfort direct appropriate care for a successful pregnancy and delivery outcome.

Attitude of Pregnant Women towards the Completion of scheduled Prenatal Check-ups and their behaviors regarding COVID-19

The majority of respondents strongly agree with the importance of checking blood pressure and other observable vital signs, with the highest score of 4.92, as well as finishing the check-ups and establishing early prenatal booking, both with a mean score of 4.80. However, there is disagreement over the importance of completing the check-ups, with some voicing concerns about the existing state of health and the potential risks involved with healthcare visits during the epidemic.

This is consistent with Westbrook's (2018) study, which revealed the need for regular prenatal check-ups and monitoring of vital signs. It provides an evidence-based approach to understanding the benefits of monitoring blood pressure and other vital indicators.

Moreover, the respondents strongly agree with the highest mean score of 4.40 that there is a risk of contracting COVID-19 during pregnancy and when leaving home during the pandemic, with a mean score of 4.38. They moderately agree on the risk of contracting COVID-19 during prenatal visits in the healthcare settings. They agree on risk of contracting COVID-19 using the facilities and equipment during prenatal clinic check-ups and on delivering and breastfeeding the baby in the hospital. The overall mean rating of 3.85 suggests an agreement among the respondents regarding these attitudes and behaviors related to COVID-19. Correspondingly, Wastnedge et al. (2021) thoroughly grasped the dangers of contracting COVID-19 during pregnancy. The importance of competent counsel in assisting pregnant mothers in making educated decisions about their own and their baby's health was mentioned. It can be inferred that while there may be a few reservations or concerns regarding the potential of COVID-19 transmission during prenatal checkups, pregnant women still express agreement or acceptance of attending these check-ups.

Pregnancy Experiences, Personal Relationships in the Barangay Health Center and information received during pregnancy care

The respondents strongly agree that they were treated politely and with respect by the healthcare personnel in the health center, the general practitioner spent enough time during their visits, and the healthcare personnel were open to their questions, cared about them, and demonstrated professional competence all with a mean score of 4.82. The overall mean rating of 4.77 suggests a high level of agreement among the respondents regarding these aspects of their healthcare experiences.

This is substantiated by Taburnal (2020), who addressed the necessity of personal relationships in the Barangay Health Center environment. It was claimed that practical advice on making meaningful connections, dealing with cultural sensitivities, and cultivating a patient-centered approach is critical in healthcare delivery.

Further, the respondents agree that they are receiving information on how their babies were developing, with the highest mean score of 4.74, along with information on breastfeeding, nutrition, and care for the child for the post-natal period, with a mean score of 4.64. With the overall mean score of 4.61 across all items, it indicates a strong agreement overall. This suggests that the respondents generally felt well-informed about various aspects of pregnancy care. Murkoff (2016) attested to the significance of a comprehensive guide for pregnant parents, which provides information and counseling on different areas of pregnancy, such as prenatal screenings, tracking the baby's progress, and caring for one's overall well-being during pregnancy.

It is worth noting that the feedback supplied by surveyed participants stressed a positive response towards their experiences particularly in obtaining the information they received during their pregnancy care. This implies that the respondents found the information valuable, helpful, and adequate healthcare services in addressing their pregnancy requirements and worries. Positive feedback could signal that healthcare practitioners or information sources effectively communicated and provided the required guidance and assistance during pregnancy.

Level of Satisfactions with Maternal Health Care

The expectant mother's level of satisfaction with maternal health care. Expectant mothers were highly satisfied with the enough availability of supplies for pregnant women, with a mean score of 4.92. This was followed by the check-ups conducted by a midwife with a mean score of 4.88. The overall mean score across all items is 4.83, indicating a high level of satisfaction overall. This indicates that the respondents were satisfied with the various components of maternal health care demonstrated in the table.

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This is validated by González-Timoneda et al. (2021), articulated the good support mechanisms in existence for midwives, focusing on their emotional well-being, worries, coping techniques, communication issues, safety precautions, and the influence of the pandemic on their professional activities.

Thereby, the high levels of satisfaction in the table confirm that the respondents highly appreciated the quality of care, information supplied, personal relationships, attention, and resources received during prenatal and postnatal care.

Factors affecting the utilization of prenatal care, respondent's attitude and pregnancy experiences on the level of satisfaction on maternal health care

Prenatal care is a crucial aspect of maternal health care, as it provides expectant mothers with regular check-ups and monitoring to ensure a healthy pregnancy and childbirth. However, despite its importance, many women do not receive adequate prenatal care, leading to poor pregnancy outcomes and increased risk of maternal mortality. Factors such as socioeconomic status, education level, and access to healthcare services have been identified as significant determinants of prenatal care utilization. Furthermore, a woman's attitude and experiences during pregnancy can also influence her level of satisfaction with maternal health care.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the findings the following conclusions are presented:

1. Participants' fears and low self-esteem prevented them from accessing prenatal care, although a pleasant psychosocial environment influenced usage. The positive attitudes of respondents regarding physical well-being and support reflect the necessity of addressing psychological aspects and creating a supportive atmosphere for pregnant mothers to prioritize prenatal care.
2. It can be inferred that there may be a few reservations or concerns regarding the risk of COVID-19 transmission during prenatal checkups, pregnant women still expressed agreement or acceptance to attending these check-ups.
3. It is worth mentioning that surveyed participants emphasized a positive reaction to their experiences, particularly in acquiring the information they received during their pregnancy care. This implies that the respondents considered the information valuable, helpful, and adequate in addressing their pregnancy requirements and worries.
4. The respondents' high levels of satisfaction confirm that they valued the quality of treatment, information provided, personal relationships, attention, and resources received during prenatal and postnatal care.
5. Psychosocial factors such as social support, the absence of domestic violence, resource availability, and confidentiality influence maternal health care satisfaction, highlighting the importance of addressing them for improved treatment quality and satisfaction among pregnant women.

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were endorsed:

1. Implement the HELP (Healthy Eating and Lifestyle during Pregnancy) Approach, which may include comprehensive education and counseling programs, to address participants' fears and low self-esteem regarding prenatal care. Creating a supportive environment through support groups, peer networks, and easily accessible mental health resources might also help pregnant mothers to prioritize and get involved in prenatal care.
2. It is recommended that more communication and education on safety measures be implemented to address concerns regarding COVID-19 transmission during prenatal check-ups. This includes clearly

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communicating infection prevention methods such as improved sanitation, social distance, and personal protective equipment. Furthermore, allotting exclusive time for pregnant women's checkups in health centers and establishing virtual appointments options for non-emergency visits can give a convenient and safe alternative while addressing any transmission concerns.

3. Continue to prioritize and improve the provision of meaningful, helpful, and appropriate healthcare services that address pregnant women' individual pregnancy needs and concerns. This can be accomplished by defining clear and complete communication, providing educational tools, and actively involving pregnant women in care decision-making processes.
4. Maintain and improve existing standards of care through the HELP (Healthy Eating and Lifestyle during Pregnancy) Approach. This can be achieved by cultivating a culture of continuous quality improvement, ensuring effective communication and information sharing, strengthening interpersonal relationships between healthcare providers and patients, and ensuring the availability of resources for comprehensive prenatal and postnatal care.
5. Through collaborations between medical institutions and community groups and agencies, pregnant women deserve the opportunity to access resources for stress management, mental health assistance, resource availability, confidentiality, and social support networks. Healthcare practitioners can increase pregnant women's quality of care and overall satisfaction by addressing psychological factors and increasing their maternal healthcare experience.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study focused on assessing the expectant mother's attitudes, pregnancy experiences, and level of satisfaction of pregnant women of Barangay Central, Balanga City, Bataan on the utilization of prenatal care amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. It limited its concern to the following: (1) respondent's attitude towards prenatal care during the COVID-19 pandemic, (2) pregnancy experiences of expectant mothers with prenatal care, pregnant mother's level of satisfaction with the maternal health care, (3) relationship between the respondent's attitude and pregnancy experiences to the level of pleasure of the maternal health care and (4) proposed Barangay Health Center Intervention Program HELP Approach "Healthy Eating and Lifestyle during Pregnancy." The subjects of the study were the currently pregnant women registered in Barangay Central Health Center Target Client List (TCL) in the year 2020. The demographic profile of expectant mothers was excluded since it has been demonstrated in numerous past research findings that it has a direct and significant impact on mothers' level of satisfaction. Nonetheless, the researcher examined the connections and relationships between mothers' attitudes and experiences during pandemic times. The present study also highlights the possibility of proposing a community-based intervention that may promote the significance of continuous and established prenatal care among pregnant women from Barangay Central, Balanga City Bataan.

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